

QC Report - Agilent Technologies : 2 Color Gene Expression

QCMetrics InRange (8 of 11)

Date	Wednesday, August 11, 2010 - 12:17	BG Method	No Background
Image	US83403541_251897210116_S01 [1_4]	Background Detrend	On(FeatNCRRange, LoPass)
Protocol	GE2_105_Dec08 (Read Only)	Multiplicative Detrend	True
User Name	melblab	Dye Norm	Linear Lowess
Grid	US83403541_251897210116_S01_grid (from grid_file)	Linear DyeNorm Factor	0.427(Red)0.553(Green)
FE Version	10.5.1.1	Additive Error	5(Red)7(Green)

Sample(red/green)

Spot Finding of the Four Corners of the Array

Evaluate Grid

Feature	Local Background	
	Red	Green

	Red	Green	Red	Green
Non Uniform	2	2	0	0
Population	87	110	1354	459

Spatial Distribution of All Outliers on the Array

532 rows x 85 columns

FeatureNonUnif (Red or Green) = 2(0.00%)

GeneNonUnif (Red or Green) = 2 (0.006 %)

- BG NonUniform ● BG Population
- Red FeaturePopulation ● Red Feature NonUniform
- Green FeaturePopulation ● Green Feature NonUniform

Net Signal Statistics

Agilent SpikeIns:

	Red	Green
# Saturated Features	0	0
99% of Sig. Distrib.	440	676
50% of Sig. Distrib.	345	485
1% of Sig. Distrib.	214	325

Non-Control probes:

	Red	Green
# Saturated Features	0	0
99% of Sig. Distrib.	66268	41106
50% of Sig. Distrib.	406	516
1% of Sig. Distrib.	185	258

Red and Green Background Corrected Signals (Non-Control Inliers)

Features (NonCtrl) with BGSubSignals < 0: 17417 (Red); 18915 (Green)

Negative Control Stats

	Red	Green
Average Net Signals	323.30	458.82
StdDev Net Signals	8.75	8.60
Average BG Sub Signal	1.91	-0.21
StdDev BG Sub Signal	7.75	8.23

Local Bkg (inliers)

	Red	Green
Number	43666	44561
Avg	54.80	26.00
SD	2.11	1.19

Foreground Surface Fit

	Red	Green
RMS_Fit	5.59	4.28
RMS_Resid	12.33	13.52
Avg_Fit	328.09	465.90

Reproducibility: %CV for Replicated Probes

Median %CV Signal (inliers)

	Non-Control probes		Agilent SpikeIns	
	Red	Green	Red	Green
BGSubSignal	11.92	11.30	-1.00	-1.00
ProcessedSignal	3.63	3.97	-1.00	-1.00

Array Uniformity: LogRatios

Non-Control Agilent SpikeIns

	Non-Control	Agilent SpikeIns
AbsAvgLogRatio	0.11	0.24
AverageS/N	7.83	3.38

Sensitivity:Agilent SpikeIns - Ratio of Signal to Background for 2 dimmest probes

(+)E1A_r60_n11		(+)E1A_r60_a97	
(g)	(r)	(g)	(r)
0.9	1.0	1.1	1.0

Spatial Distribution of Significantly Up-Regulated and Down-Regulated Features

#Up-Regulated:2005 (Red) ; #Down-Regulated:2037 (Green)

▲ Up-Regulated □ Down-Regulated

LogRatio Versus Log Processed Signal

- Significantly down regulated
- Significantly up regulated
- Used to normalize
- Not differentially expressed

Agilent SpikeIns Signal Statistics

Probe Name	Exp	Obs	SD	S/N
(+)E1A_r60_n9	-1.00	-0.13	0.07	1.89
(+)E1A_r60_a107	-0.48	***	***	***
(+)E1A_r60_a135	-0.48	-0.45	0.08	6.06
(+)E1A_r60_n11	-0.48	-0.02	0.08	0.24
(+)E1A_r60_1	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.18
(+)E1A_r60_a20	0.00	***	***	***
(+)E1A_r60_3	0.48	-0.45	0.15	3.01
(+)E1A_r60_a104	0.48	-0.39	0.04	10.34
(+)E1A_r60_a97	0.48	0.21	0.09	2.44
(+)E1A_r60_a22	1.00	-0.30	0.10	2.86

Evaluation Metrics for GE2_QCMT_Dec08

Metric Name	Value	UpLim	LowLim	IsMandatory
AnyColorPrcntFeatNonUnif...	0.00	1.00	NA	False
absE1aObsVsExpCorr	0.02	NA	0.86	False
absE1aObsVsExpSlope	0.05	NA	0.85	False
gE1aMedCVBkSubSignal	-1.00	25.00	NA	False
gNegCtrlAveBGSubSig	-0.21	10.00	-20.00	False
gNegCtrlSDevBGSubSig	8.23	15.00	NA	False
gNonCntrlMedCVBkSubSignal	11.30	25.00	NA	False
rE1aMedCVBkSubSignal	-1.00	25.00	NA	False
rNegCtrlAveBGSubSig	1.91	4.00	-20.00	False
rNegCtrlSDevBGSubSig	7.75	6.00	NA	False
rNonCntrlMedCVBkSubSignal	11.92	25.00	NA	False

◆ In Normal Range ◆ Evaluate

Agilent SpikeIns: % CV of Average BG Sub Signal

Agilent SpikeIns: Expected LogRatio Vs Observed LogRatio

